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Introduction

	Channels	Unit	Channel No
1	Displacement – Shake Table	m	5
2	Acceleration – Shake Table	g	12
3	Acceleration – Wall Bottom Quarter	g	15
4	Acceleration – Wall Middle	g	16
5	Acceleration – Wall Top Quarter	g	17

Baseline Correction	: On - Average
Filter Low-cut	: 0.25 Hz
Filter High-cut	: 50 Hz
Filter Order	: 3
Spectrum Window Size	: 30 seconds
Spectrum Window Overlap	: %50
Spectrum Resolution	: 0.033 Hz
Spectrum Smoothing	: 9 Data Points

Analysis steps:

- Finding the point where the excitation ends and free vibration starts from the shake table displacement measurement.
- Trimming the acceleration time series from the channels/sensors located at the shake table and wall (bottom quarter, mid, and top quarter).
- Signal processing of the time series data, including offset correction and band-pass filtering.
- Estimation of the Periodogram of the signals, calculation of PSD, and Singular Values.
- Peak-picking of the dominant frequencies.

For the vibration analysis of the model, total of five channels are used. One originates from the shake table displacement, serving as the input motion, and is utilized to determine the start of free vibration. The remaining four channels consist of acceleration measurements: one is mounted on the shake table to capture input motion, while the others are positioned at various heights on the wall.

For each test, the first (1st) and last (24th) runs are analyzed. Dominant frequencies are determined from the Singular Values of the channels. The first mode has a natural frequency between 9-11 Hz, while the second mode has a frequency range of 18.3-18.9 Hz, depending on the amplitude of excitation and the model. The relationship between different tests and runs is provided in the **Results** section.

Test 9 – US1

Run 1

Acceleration Time Series - Free Vibration

Power Spectral Density

Run 24

Acceleration Time Series - Free Vibration

Power Spectral Density

Test 10 – ST1 – FDM

Run 1

Run 24

Acceleration Time Series - Free Vibration

Power Spectral Density

Test 11 – ST2 – HB

Run 1

Run 24

Test 12 – US2

Run 1

Run 24

Acceleration Time Series - Free Vibration

Power Spectral Density

Result

Data Table

		Period (s)			
		Test9-US1	Test10-ST1	Test11-ST2	Test12-US2
Mode 1	Run1	0.091	0.086	0.084	0.089
	Run24	0.113	0.095	0.088	0.102